

SOP: Using the Registration User Interface

How to register tissue blocks to reference organs

Authors: Andreas Bueckle, Katy Börner, Bruce W. Herr II

Approved by: Katy Börner (8/30/21), Bruce W. Herr II (8/26/2021)

HIVE MC-IU Team, Indiana University

PI: Katy Börner

NIH Award No: 1OT2OD026671

Updated: 8/30/21

Introduction

This document contains instructions for spatially registering human tissue to a 3D reference organ using the Registration User Interface (RUI). This SOP is written for HuBMAP members that would like to upload tissue data via the [HuBMAP Ingest Portal](#) and for users not affiliated with the HuBMAP consortium who would like to register data using the [public RUI](#).

The latest video demo of RUI version 1.7.0 (06/07/2021) can be found [here](#).

Flowchart of RUI Registration Procedure

If accessing the RUI via the Ingest Portal

If accessing the RUI standalone version

Versions of the Registration User Interface

Two versions of the RUI exist, and which one you access depends on whether you are registering tissue blocks via the HuBMAP Ingest Portal or not.

1. If the tissue block you are registering is affiliated with the HuBMAP consortium, go to the [HuBMAP Ingest Portal](#) and follow the instructions [below](#). Metadata such as author name, date, etc. is captured as part of the tissue ingest process and RUI data is automatically associated with the tissue on Globus.
2. If the tissue block you are registering is not affiliated with HuBMAP, go to the [public RUI](#). You will need to enter your first and last name and select the organ for which you are registering tissue blocks. You will download the RUI data in JSON format and share it with the MC-IU team. The RUI data will then be placed [into this folder](#) and be made available via the public CCF [Exploration User Interface](#). Instructions on how to use the RUI are [below](#).
3. The difference between the HuBMAP (accessed via the Ingest Portal) and the public RUI is that the HuBMAP version facilitates submission of the registration data via the HuBMAP Ingest Portal. When opening the RUI from within the Ingest Portal, it appears embedded in the sample registration page.

Accessing the RUI from within the HuBMAP Ingest Portal

DISCLAIMER: Although current at the time this SOP was adopted, the steps outlined here may change with future updates to the Ingest Portal. Screenshots may not always reflect what you see when you access the Ingest Portal.

Case 1: Register a new sample with RUI location

This section outlines how to access the RUI from the HuBMAP Ingest Portal to register a new sample with HuBMAP and register its location via the RUI at the same time.

1. Visit <https://ingest.hubmapconsortium.org>
2. If needed, log in using your institutional credentials.

3. Click the Sample tab on the top to see existing samples or to register a new sample.

HuBMAP REGISTER NEW: DONOR SAMPLE ahuocke@hu.edu EDIT PROFILE LOGOUT

Search

Use the filter controls to search for Donors, Samples, Datasets or Data Uploads. If you know a specific ID you can enter it into the keyword field to locate individual entities.

Group: All Components Type: ---

Enter a keyword or HuBMAP/Submission/Lab ID. For wildcard searches use * e.g., VAN004*

HuBMAP ID	Submission ID	Lab ID	Type	Group Name	Created By
HBM335.CRPJ.792	VAN0062.RK.5	213	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM539.TNDH.662	VAN0062.RK.4	212	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM963.ZNBR.996	VAN0062.RK.3	211	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM767.MZMK.729	VAN0062.RK.2	210	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM799.CVNH.972	VAN0062.RK.1	209	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM576.NLVW.835	VAN0062.RK	73603	Kidney (Right)	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM586.SDZD.467	VAN0062	209-213	Donor	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM629.PWVK.488	VAN0061.LK.4	204	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM528.SNHZ.796	VAN0061.LK.3	203	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu

Rows per page: 100 1-100 of 10000

4. Click the Source ID text input field. This will prompt search for a Source ID for your Sample.

HuBMAP REGISTER NEW: DONOR SAMPLE DATASET ahuocke@hu.edu EDIT PROFILE LOGOUT

Sample Information

 Do not provide any Protected Health Information. This includes the 18 identifiers specified by HIPAA

Source ID

Tissue Sample Type

Preparation Protocol

Generate IDs for multiple samples

Lab Sample Id

Description

Sample Metadata Status

Upload de-identified images only

Search for a Source ID for your Sample

Use the filter controls to search for Donors, Samples, Datasets or Data Uploads. If you know a specific ID you can enter it into the keyword field to locate individual entities.

Group: All Components Type: ---

Enter a keyword or HuBMAP/Submission/Lab ID. For wildcard searches use * e.g., VAN004*

HuBMAP ID	Submission ID	Lab ID	Type	Group Name	Created By
HBM335.CRPJ.792	VAN0062.RK.5	213	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM539.TNDH.662	VAN0062.RK.4	212	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM963.ZNBR.996	VAN0062.RK.3	211	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM767.MZMK.729	VAN0062.RK.2	210	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM799.CVNH.972	VAN0062.RK.1	209	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM576.NLVW.835	VAN0062.RK	73603	Kidney (Right)	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM586.SDZD.467	VAN0062	209-213	Donor	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM629.PWVK.488	VAN0061.LK.4	204	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu
HBM528.SNHZ.796	VAN0061.LK.3	203	Fresh frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC	jamie.lallen@vanderbilt.edu

Rows per page: 100 1-100 of 10000

CLOSE

5. Click the Group dropdown menu and choose your component.

Search for a Source ID for your Sample

Use the filter controls to search for Donors, Samples, Datasets or Data Uploads. If you know a specific ID you can enter it into the keyword field to locate individual entities.

Group: All Components

Type: ---

Enter a keyword or HuBMAP/Submission/Lab ID. For wildcard searches use * e.g. VAN004*

Clear

Group Name	Created By
frozen tissue	Vanderbilt TMC
HBM576.NLVW.835	VAN0062-RK 73603 Kidney (Right) Vanderbilt TMC
HBM586.SDZD.467	VAN0062 209-213 Donor Vanderbilt TMC
HBM629.PWIX.489	VAN0061-LK-4 204 Fresh frozen tissue Vanderbilt TMC
HBM328.SNHZ.796	VAN0061-LK-3 203 Fresh frozen tissue Vanderbilt TMC

Rows per page: 100 1-100 of 10000

CLOSE

6. Click the Type dropdown menu and select Organ.

Search for a Source ID for your Sample

Use the filter controls to search for Donors, Samples, Datasets or Data Uploads. If you know a specific ID you can enter it into the keyword field to locate individual entities.

Group: All Components

Type: ---

Enter a keyword or HuBMAP/Submission/Lab ID. For wildcard searches use * e.g. VAN004*

Search

Donor

Organ

Data Upload

HuBMAP ID	Submission ID	Lab ID	Type
HBM335.CRHJ.792	VAN0062-RK-5	213	Fresh froz
HBM539.TNDH.662	VAN0062-RK-4	212	Fresh froz
HBM963.ZNBR.996	VAN0062-RK-3	211	Fresh froz
HBM767.MZMK.729	VAN0062-RK-2	210	Fresh froz
HBM799.CVNH.972	VAN0062-RK-1	209	Fresh froz
HBM576.NLVW.835	VAN0062-RK	73603	Kidney (Right) Vanderbilt TMC
HBM586.SDZD.467	VAN0062	209-213	Donor Vanderbilt TMC
HBM629.PWIX.489	VAN0061-LK-4	204	Fresh frozen tissue Vanderbilt TMC
HBM328.SNHZ.796	VAN0061-LK-3	203	Fresh frozen tissue Vanderbilt TMC

Rows per page: 100 1-100 of 10000

CLOSE

7. Click Search.

Search for a Source ID for your Sample

Use the filter controls to search for Donors, Samples, Datasets or Data Uploads. If you know a specific ID you can enter it into the keyword field to locate individual entities.

Group: Type:

Enter a keyword or HuBMAP/Submission/Lab ID. For wildcard searches use * e.g., VAN004*

HuBMAP ID	Submission ID	Lab ID	Type	Group Name	Created By
HBM576.NLWV.835	VAN0062-RK	73603	Kidney (Right)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM267.PC0M.735	VAN0061-LK	73424	Kidney (Left)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM963.QRDW.388	VAN0060-LK	72928	Kidney (Left)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM537.BXGZ.377	VAN0059-RK	74083	Kidney (Right)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM682.LR9F.428	VAN0058-RK	74501	Kidney (Right)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM623.MXTT.433	VAN0057-LK	75905	Kidney (Left)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM737.RTCP.923	VAN0056-LK	76761	Kidney (Left)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM426.F5CZ.845	VAN0055-RK	69857	Kidney (Right)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM962.RV6Z.629	VAN0054-LK	73539	Kidney (Left)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt

Rows per page: 100 1-100 of 293

CLOSE

8. A list of organs is displayed. Pick one by clicking its row.

Search for a Source ID for your Sample

Use the filter controls to search for Donors, Samples, Datasets or Data Uploads. If you know a specific ID you can enter it into the keyword field to locate individual entities.

Group: Type:

Enter a keyword or HuBMAP/Submission/Lab ID. For wildcard searches use * e.g., VAN004*

HuBMAP ID	Submission ID	Lab ID	Type	Group Name	Created By
HBM576.NLWV.835	VAN0062-RK	73603	Kidney (Right)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM267.PC0M.735	VAN0061-LK	73424	Kidney (Left)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM963.QRDW.388	VAN0060-LK	72928	Kidney (Left)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM537.BXGZ.377	VAN0059-RK	74083	Kidney (Right)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM682.LR9F.428	VAN0058-RK	74501	Kidney (Right)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM623.MXTT.433	VAN0057-LK	75905	Kidney (Left)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM737.RTCP.923	VAN0056-LK	76761	Kidney (Left)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM426.F5CZ.845	VAN0055-RK	69857	Kidney (Right)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt
HBM962.RV6Z.629	VAN0054-LK	73539	Kidney (Left)	Vanderbilt TMC	james.lallen@vanderbilt

Rows per page: 100 1-100 of 293

CLOSE

9. This returns you to the Sample Information page, displaying the newly added Source ID. Click the Tissue Sample Type dropdown menu and select the appropriate entry.

HuBMAP REGISTER NEW? DONOR SAMPLE DATA? shuckie@u.vanderbilt.edu EDIT PROFILE LOGOUT

Sample Information

Do not provide any Protected Health Information. This includes the ID identifiers specified by HIPAA.

Source ID:

Source Type: Fresh frozen tissue
Submission ID: VAN0062-RK-5
Group Name: Vanderbilt TMC

Tissue Sample Type:

- Biospy
- Cell System
- FFPE block
- FFPE block
- FFA Fixed frozen OCT block
- Fixed tissue piece
- Flash frozen liquid nitrogen
- Formalin fixed OCT block
- Fresh frozen tissue
- Fresh frozen w/ block
- Fresh tissue
- Frozen cell pellet (bulky coat)
- Module
- PRMC
- Plasma
- Nucleic RNA later
- Organ Piece
- RNA later treated and stored
- Segment

Upload an identified image only

10. Fill out the other fields as needed, then start the registration process by pressing the blue Register Location button.

HuBMAP REGISTER NEW: DONOR SAMPLE DATASET abueckle@iu.edu EDIT PROFILE LOGOUT

Sample Information

- Do not provide any Protected Health Information. This includes the 18 identifiers specified by HIPAA

Source ID *

Source Type: Fresh frozen tissue
Submission ID: VAN0062-RK-5
Group Name: Vanderbilt TMC

Tissue Sample Type *

Fresh frozen tissue

Preparation Protocol *

Generate IDs for multiple Fresh frozen tissue samples

Lab Sample Id

Sample Location

Register Location

Description

Sample Metadata Status

No value set

Add a Metadata File

Add an Image file

Upload de-identified images only

Generate ID Cancel

11. The RUI is displayed, embedded into the page, with the organ of your choice selected.

12. Follow the steps outlined in the Tissue Placement section for the next steps to place tissue.

13. When done, click the Generate ID button in the Ingest Portal.

Case 2: Adding a RUI location to an existing sample

1. Repeat steps 1, 2, and 5 from the section on [registering a new sample with RUI location](#). You can also enter a HuBMAP ID to find the sample in question. Then, instead of opening the Type dropdown menu, just click the Search button.
2. Select the tissue for which you would like to register a RUI location. Click the Register Location button to access the RUI.
3. Follow steps 12-13 from the section on [registering a new sample with RUI location](#).
4. If your data is unpublished, you can add a RUI location to an existing sample without prior permission from the IEC at any time. **For a short period of time, you can also add a RUI location to published, unregistered samples.**

Registration Procedures

The registration process works as follows:

5. The RUI currently supports a limited number of organs. Check whether the RUI supports your organ by opening the standalone version of the RUI and checking the organ carousel: <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-ui/rui/>
6. Gather any materials needed to document where the tissue block was extracted from.
7. Open the relevant version of the RUI (see [above](#) to determine which version of the RUI you need to use).
8. When opening the [public RUI](#), you are presented with a small window as it loads. Here you can adjust settings, including the following parameters.
9. Name
 - a. In the public version, enter your first and last name into the corresponding text entry fields.
 - b. In the Ingest Portal version, your name is already captured on the back end based on data from your user profile.
10. Donor sex and organ selection:
 - a. Select the donor's sex
 - b. In the public version, select an organ from the organ carousel. Make sure to select the right or left version as appropriate. The organ might take a few seconds to load.
 - c. In the Ingest Portal version, the organ is pre-selected.

Tissue Placement

11. For a step-by-step demonstration, please watch [this demo](#).

12. Resize the tissue block using the Tissue Block Dimensions text input fields in the top right corner. The default is a 10x10x10 mm block.
13. Move the tissue block into position by clicking and dragging the left mouse button over the tissue block. Note that in order for the tissue block to be movable, the radio buttons in the top left corner of the 3D window have to be set to either Left, Right, Anterior, or Posterior. When set to 3D, the tissue block cannot be moved.
14. The tissue block can only be moved in two dimensions at a time.
 - a. To make “looking inside” the reference organ easier, all anatomical structures are set to 20% opacity as the default. You can adjust the opacity using the Anatomical Structures accordion menu in the metadata pane (see [below](#)).
 - b. To inspect tissue blocks you placed before (for reference), click the Previously Registered Blocks toggle button in the metadata pane on the left. Clicking this toggle button will show all previously registered tissue blocks based on your browser’s local cache.
 - c. To change the perspective, use the radio buttons in the 3D pane (see [below](#)).
 - d. To verify the placement, switch to 3D Preview mode using the corresponding toggle switch at the top of the 3D pane (see [below](#)).
15. Adjust the rotation of the tissue block by using the rotation sliders in the manipulation pane on the right.

To finalize the registration

16. If you are using the Ingest Portal version of the RUI, click the Register Location button. The RUI window will then close automatically.
17. If you are using the public version of the RUI, click the Review and Download button in the bottom right corner of the screen to review the data and download it as a JSON file. A Registration Review window pops up, where you can check the validity of the data you generated. You can then download the JSON file to your hard drive.

Description of the user interface (UI)

Figure 1: The stand-alone CCF Registration User Interface (RUI) currently supports tissue registration for 11 organs: skin, large intestine, heart, kidney (left/right), spleen, brain, lungs, lymph nodes (left/right), pelvis, thymus, and vasculature. The yellow cuboid represents the tissue block. The green slide indicates the bisection line inside the kidney. Tissue block size and rotation can be adjusted on the right. Anatomical structure tags (bottom right) are automatically assigned based on 3D collision with semantically annotated 3D reference objects. Users can add additional tags using the text input field.

Figure 2: The RUI has three panes: metadata (yellow), 3D (pink), and manipulation (blue).

The RUI consists of three panes: the metadata pane on the left, the 3D pane in the middle, and the manipulation pane on the right, see Fig. 2. Here are brief explanations of what can be accomplished in each pane:

- a. The metadata pane contains the following elements:
 - i. Donor Sex: enter the sex of the tissue donor.
 - ii. Anatomical Structures menu: The anatomical structures listed here correspond to 3D structures inside the reference organ. A slider appears when the user hovers over the drop icon to the left of the anatomical structure text entry, allowing one to adjust the opacity of the structure. This allows the user to make certain parts of the organ more transparent than others, allowing them to retain certain structures as landmarks while placing the tissue block. Also, clicking the eye icon to the right of the slider will hide the structure. It can be turned on by clicking the icon again.
 - iii. Common Extraction Sites menu: When hovering over a drop icon, the Common Extraction Sites menu reveals frequently used extraction locations, such as the apex for the heart. Extraction sites can also serve as important landmarks (such as the bisection line for the kidney). All extraction sites are hidden by default. Extraction sites are rendered green.
 - iv. Previously Registered Blocks toggle button: This button allows you to view tissue blocks you have registered before, which show as blue in the 3D pane. This information is taken from your browser cache. When previously registered blocks are shown, anatomical structure opacity is reduced to 20%.
- b. The 3D pane contains the reference organ and the tissue block. It is a 3D window, similar to what one would find in 3D modeling software or a video game. In the top left corner, a set of radio buttons allow the user to control the 3D camera of the scene.
 - i. Using the radio buttons labeled Left, Right, Anterior, and Posterior, the user can rotate the camera around the reference organ in increments of 90 degrees. The current camera view is visually indicated by a small human icon on the right side of the 3D pane.
 - ii. When Left, Right, Anterior, or Posterior are clicked, the camera movement is restricted to 90 degree increments, and the mouse is used to move the tissue block. Select 3D Preview to verify tissue placement. When in 3D Preview mode, the user can rotate the camera at two degrees of freedom while clicking and dragging the left mouse button. The user can also zoom in by using the mouse scroll wheel (or whatever input method is assigned to scrolling) and pan the camera (i.e., move it laterally) by clicking and dragging the right mouse button.
 - iii. In the top right corner, the current x, y, z-coordinates of the tissue block are shown, with the origin in the back bottom left corner of the reference organ.

- iv. The circular arrow in the top right corner of the 3D pane can be used to reset the position of the tissue block.
- c. The manipulation pane on the right allows the user to resize and rotate the tissue block, indicate thickness and number of slices, and review anatomical structure tags generated via collision detection between the tissue block and the anatomical structures in the reference organ.
 - i. On the top of the manipulation pane, the Tissue Block Dimensions fields allow the user to define the size of the tissue block in millimeters (mm). These fields can be reset by clicking the small circular arrow button in the top right.
 - ii. Below that, the Tissue Slices fields let the user indicate the thickness and number of slices for the tissue block. Note that the thickness is indicated in micrometers (μm). These fields can be reset by clicking the small circular arrow button in the top-right.
 - iii. The Tissue Block Rotation sliders allow the user to add rotation to each axis of the tissue block individually. The sliders are color coded (red: x, green: y, blue: z). All slider values can be reset by clicking the small circular arrow button in the top-right. Note that the RUI is a “y-up” 3D application where the y-axis corresponds to the global “up” vector.
 - iv. The Anatomical Structure Tags menu can be expanded via a click. This section is empty by default but is automatically filled as the user moves the tissue block into the reference organ. Once a collision between an anatomical structure and the tissue block has been detected, the name of the anatomical structure is added to the Anatomical Structure Tags section as a tag. Tags can be removed by clicking on the little X to the right of the tag. Tags can also be added manually. Anatomical structures must be selected from the auto-complete suggestions provided.

References and Definitions

The below references and definitions were used in writing this Standard Operating Procedure. When available, definitions were taken from the [HuBMAP Dictionary](#), and aligned with standard terminologies used in relevant fields.

References

- The public Common Coordinate Framework Registration User Interface (CCF RUI): <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-ui/rui>. Accessed on Feb 20, 2021.
- HuBMAP Ingest Portal: <https://ingest.hubmapconsortium.org>.
- RUI ingest flowchart: <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1bCX0XusohrvLqoo44ygob3-aAQB6-ei7MMiog7Q75ag/edit#slide=id.p1>. Accessed on Aug 30, 2021.

- The CCF Portal: <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf>. Accessed on Feb 20, 2021.

Glossary

HuBMAP: The Human BioMolecular Atlas Program is a consortium composed of diverse research teams funded by the [Common Fund at the National Institutes of Health](#). HuBMAP is developing the tools to create an open, global atlas of the human body at the cellular level. These tools and maps will be openly available, to accelerate understanding of the relationships between cell and tissue organization and function and human health.

HuBMAP Ingest Portal: The HuBMAP Ingest Portal is where HuBMAP members generate HuBMAP IDs.

Globus: Globus is software-as-a-service for research data management, used by hundreds of research institutions and HPC facilities worldwide for secure, reliable file transfer, sharing and publication. (Globus.org)

Reference Organ: A reference organ is a 3D model based on a variety of potential data sources produced by MC-IU. 3D models are created with the involvement of subject matter experts. [This SOP](#) outlines the creation of reference organs.

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs): SOPs are issued to specifically instruct team members in areas of responsibility, procedural steps, appropriate specifications and required records. SOPs outline procedures, which must be followed to support the reproducibility of scientific research. Procedures can take the form of a narrative, a flow chart, a process map, computer screen printouts or combination of all or any other suitable form, however must be written in appropriate, effective grammatical style. (e.g. plain English).

Tissue Block: A tissue block is a digital, 3D representation of a tissue sample. In the RUI, tissue blocks are cuboids that the user can spatially register to a reference organ.